

THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION INFORMATION ACTIVITIES UZBEK JOURNALIST

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Abstract. *This scientific paper underlines the importance of preserving cultural identity in the face of globalization, analyzing the information activities of Uzbek journalists. It focuses on the transformation of systematic approaches, content saturation, and presentation of journalistic material. The study explores how these changes create new communication processes in the national media landscape, which have a global impact on public consciousness and interaction between cultures of various ethnic groups residing in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *information activity, journalist mentality, information globalization, multimedia content, media processes.*

Introduction

Uzbekistan has unique human, regional, innovative, technological, tourism and media potential. The coexistence of many nationalities in one territory ensures a

centuries-old flow and mutual penetration and influence of cultures. All this is reflected in the media. The media image of the region does not stand still; it constantly develops and changes as a “living” organism ready for integration, reform, and progress. Undoubtedly, globalization impacts the individual, activating the interaction between television as a cultural agitator and the audience, influencing all spheres of the individual's life. “The fundamental basis of globalization should be considered the revolution in communication, communication, and informatics, which radically changed the nature of intellectual, cultural, and technological interaction between individual components of world civilization.” (Inozemtsev V.L., 2006)

Today, media processes in Uzbekistan are adapting to modern reality and undergoing rapid innovative transformations. For instance, the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan, a professional media monolith, is embracing new media technologies and platforms, such as private and Internet television. These changes are shaping a fundamentally different mass media landscape in Uzbekistan, directly related to the rapidly changing conditions in the world and serious domestic and international social, economic, political, and cultural transformations.

If we look at the Uzbekistan TV industry, such projects are available on almost every channel. Moreover, each channel can boast its own “people” who provide visualization and an overall television ranking. After all, it is known that the interaction of a presenter's professional and personal qualities ensures a strong connection with the television audience and has a powerful mechanism of influencing it. The personalized host begins to be viewed by the viewer on the other side of the screen as a friend, a close person whose views can be trusted, and a natural partner whose opinion can be relied on. The phenomenon of its popularity, according to M. Moskovisi, expresses “the need of large social groups for an informal leader, a leader, on whom they can rely in their individual, group, and national behavior.” (Moskovichi S., 1998)

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Live broadcast. There were no spectators in the studios, but more calls for live broadcasts. Live broadcast themes have also been adjusted. If, previously, entertainment content was the central part of TV programs, then with the arrival of the coronavirus infection, people began to care about their health, and programs dedicated to treating and preventing this disease began to beat all the ratings of global views. For example, I can cite the “Online consultation” project on the “Oilaviy” TV channel of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan. At least, the rising rating can be judged by the advertisers who rushed into the project to place their own advertising products. Ad revenue for the channel has increased more than tenfold over the past year. “Television broadcasting is a highly effective form of advertising goods and propaganda of ideas, capable of simultaneously influencing a multi-million audience and inducing them to make certain decisions (in the most direct way – when buying something)” (Vasiliev A.D., 2000).

We must recognize the mental orientation of the speech and how the modern Uzbek TV presenter thinks. Despite the possible sharpness of the topics raised in the live broadcast, the Uzbek host still maintains maximum respect for the interlocutor,

keeping the line of culture and upbringing the same, unlike, for example, Western or Russian journalists. “The East is a fine thing. It is reflected in everything: lifestyle, mentality, culture, spiritual values.” “If the West actively changes reality to suit its needs and desires, then a person with an Eastern mentality prefers to preserve himself and his group despite the pressure of temptations and fashionable trends.” (Muller M., 2020) (http://www.mentality.com/). It is known that mentality is particularly pronounced in stressful situations. According to S. Lukyanenko, “We look at the world through the thick curved glasses we were given in childhood. These glasses are education, culture, and mentality. You can never get rid of them.” (Quotes about mentality)

There is a general trend towards live broadcasts on modern Uzbek television, including entertainment content. As well as the constant preservation of the culture of behavior and mentality in the speech of Uzbek journalists and TV presenters. Sh. M. Niyaziliyev states that the psychology of a people “manifests itself in typical features of people's character, in their feelings, temperament, needs, tastes, prejudices, habits, will and other psychological phenomena, which are fixed by customs and traditions, fixed in the forms of culture, passed down from generation to generation.” (Niyazaliev Sh.M., 1986)

To become such a person on television in the era of information globalization, in the conditions of a market economy and competition, it is necessary to take into account the demands of the time and develop the following skills:

1. *Adaptation to multimedia content:* Uzbek television journalists are effectively adapting to multimedia communication requirements, combining traditional work methods with new technologies. They create content for television, Internet platforms, social networks, and mobile applications, which requires expanding their professional skills.

2. *Development of digital skills:* Uzbek television journalists are increasingly mastering digital tools and technologies necessary for multimedia. This

includes using analytical tools, mastering new content creation and editing programs, and working with social media to interact with the audience.

3. *Multitasking and cross-functionality*: Modern requirements for TV journalists in Uzbekistan require them to perform several functions simultaneously, such as gathering information, writing text, creating video content and interacting with the audience through various channels, conducting online broadcasts, creating interactive materials, and using social media to get feedback from viewers. This requires a high degree of flexibility and multitasking.

4. *Ethical and professional standards*: In the context of multimedia communication, ethical norms and professional responsibility become more important. Uzbek television journalists face challenges in ensuring the reliability of information, preventing the spread of fake news, and maintaining a balance of opinions.

5. *Influence of cultural and socio-political factors*: Uzbekistan's unique cultural and socio-political contexts significantly impact the work of television journalists. They should consider local characteristics and audiences when creating content, influencing approaches to providing information, and choosing topics.

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GLOBALLASHUVNING O'ZBEK JURNALISTINING AXBORIY FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya. *Mazkur ilmiy maqolada globallashuv sharoitida madaniy o'zlikni saqlashning ahamiyati, o'zbek jurnalistlarining axborot faoliyati tahlili yoritilgan. Unda tizimli yondashuvlar transformatsiyasi, mazmunga to'yinganlik, publitsistik materialni taqdim etishga e'tibor qaratilgan. Tadqiqotda ushbu o'zgarishlar milliy media manzarasida ijtimoiy ong va O'zbekistonda stiqomat qiluvchi turli etnik guruhlarining madaniyatlari o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirga global ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi yangi kommunikatsiya jarayonlarini qanday yaratishi ochib berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: axboriy faoliyat, jurnalistning mentaliteti, axborotning globallashuvi, multimediamiy kontent, mediajarayonlar.